

Protocol for semi-structured interviews: Modellers

Interview openings

1. Introduce interviewer and recap on project, interview aims and duration. Highlight the scope of this interview as regarding the EU level.
2. Double check on ethical procedures: Participant Information Sheet seen, Consent Form signed, including consent for audio recording interview.

Indicative questions and discussion prompts to aid interview discussion

1. Introductory and participant background questions
 - Please tell me about your current role and main work areas?
 - Please tell me about your professional background (e.g. past roles and academic disciplinary background)?
2. Describing current understanding of policy evaluation
 - Can you tell me about how you would approach policy evaluation? Are there standard approaches that you know of (e.g. UK Government 'Green Book', cost-benefit analysis)?
 - What are the criteria or standards that constitute a "good" outcome according to these current approaches to evaluation?
 - Do you feel the policy appraisal process should consider uncertainty, diversity of actors, long time horizons, innovation or radical transformation of markets?
3. Describing current use of models
 - What does the term 'model' mean to you?
 - Which models do you work on/with?
 - How and to what extent do you work with models that predict policy outcomes? How and to what extent do you work with models that appraise impacts of existing policies?
 - To what extent are your model/models taken up by policyworkers; would you describe this as a more or less dominant model at present? If this varies across contexts, please explain how and why.
 - At which point(s) in the policy process are these models or outputs used; for what purposes do you think they are used?
4. Exploring models (If multiple models are within their remit, repeat these questions for each model)
 - What do you see as the strengths or advantages of your model?
 - What do you see as the limitations or disadvantages of this model?
 - How do you compare your model outputs to reality (do you use data for calibration or sensitivity testing on future scenarios)?
 - What are the most important differences between your model and others?
 - What are the main assumptions of this model; what does it include and exclude, what type of data is used as input, does it have investment requirements for computation capacity?
5. Experiences of using models to inform policy
 - Can you tell me about any times when model outputs have had tangible impacts on policy (for example, specific documents drawing on model outputs)?
 - Have there been instances when models/outputs have not been used so effectively; or have not had the desired effect on policy – if so, can you describe what happened and why? (This includes models having less effect than expected, but also having any negative effects)

- Other than direct policy influence, can you tell me about any ways that models and their outputs have had impacts outside academia?
 - Have there been instances when you have had to alter or adapt your models or their outputs because of policy considerations; if so, what happened and why?
 - Thinking back to the limitations or disadvantages you mentioned earlier, how do these affect the way that you present the model/outputs? (Are there certain ways in which you would recommend it should not be used?)
6. Communities and cultures around models
- To what extent do you engage with policymakers and discuss their needs and priorities, and what your model can/cannot offer?
 - At what stage of model development do you engage with policymakers (before designing models, during the modelling process, to run outputs as requested or to adapt models to respond to specific requests)?
 - Are there clear gaps where models could be improved or developed to better inform policy making? If yes what are they?
 - To what extent do policymakers understand your work and its outputs; have you encountered any challenges when engaging with them?
 - Within the modelling community, what are the main schools of thought, clusters/types or dividing lines? Where do you see yourself within this?
7. Alternative and wider perspectives
- In what ways could the models you use, or the way they are applied, be improved?
 - To what extent have you considered using approaches other than modelling to achieve the goals we have been discussing? (refer back to answer under theme 2, if helpful)
 - What other kinds of data and methods are (or might be) useful in complementing the models you use?

Interview closings

1. Ask if there is anything further the interviewee wishes to add.
2. Thank the interviewee for their time.
3. Explain next steps and outputs of the project.